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First record of *Dendropsophus frosti* (Amphibia, Anura, Hylidae) in Brazil, with comments on its reproductive behaviour

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D*endropsophus* Fitzinger, 1843 is a hylid genus that occurs from southern South America through the neotropical region to southern Mexico, with 109 described species (Frost, 2022). Many species of this genus are still unknown, or poorly studied (Orrico et al., 2021). *Dendropsophus frosti* Motta, Castroviejo-Fisher, Venegas, Orrico, and Padiá, 2012 is a medium sized *Dendropsophus* with snout-vent length of males ranging from 21.1 to 23.0 mm and of females from 25.9 to 28.8 mm (Motta et al., 2012). The species calls at night perched in low vegetation and lays terrestrial eggs attached to adaxial surface of herbaceous plant leaves above water (Motta et al., 2012). The only known re-

records of this species are from Colombia, municipality of Leticia, state of Amazonas and Peru, municipality of Piedras, state of Loreto, both in the *terra firme* forests of the Amazon basin (Motta et al., 2012). A member of the *Dendropsophus parviceps* group and *D. subocularis* clade (Orrico et al., 2021), *D. frosti* conspicuously differs from all other species of the genus that occur in the region, and even from the other species of its group. Herein, we report the first record of *D. frosti* from Brazil, and provide an updated distribution map. We also comment on undescribed reproductive characters from a population near the type locality, providing photos of a male, an amplexant pair and a clutch.

We collected four specimens of *D. frosti* at Santos Dumont Street, Tabatinga municipality, Amazonas state, Brazil (-4.232417, -69.911194; Fig. 1) between April and September 2019 and in April 2021, between 18h00 and 22h00. We also examined four specimens in the Zoological Collection Paulo Burnheim of the Universidade Federal do Amazonas (CZPB, Manaus, Amazonas, Brazil), collected on the right bank of the Japurá River, Japurá Municipality, Amazonas state, Brazil (-1.846139, -69.029528; Fig. 1) between August and September 2014. These specimens were deposited at the Zoological Collection Paulo Burnheim of the Universidade Federal do Amazonas (CZPB-AA 1552-1555, 2156, 2158, 2159 and 2244). Along with these eight collected specimens we analyzed the morphology of 11 not collected specimens recorded during the fieldwork in Tabatinga municipality.

To confirm identification, specimens were compared to the species' description, following the nomenclature used in the diagnosis (Motta et al., 2012). All individuals exhibited the principal diagnostic characters, which combined make the species differ from all its congeners, and from the other species of the *D. parviceps* group: (i) dorsum smooth, light brown, (ii) flanks dark brown, (iii) fingers IV and V and toes III and IV dark brown, (iv) venter pale brown, (v) fingers I and II, toes I and II,

and tip of the finger III and toe III pale brown, (vi) iris copper; (vii) suborbital bars absent (Fig. 2).

On April 29, 2021 after two days of intense rainfall in the municipality of Tabatinga we observed a reproductive event. Several males were calling perched in the herbaceous vegetation, about 1 to 2 m above the ground, near a natural permanent pond connected to a stream (Fig. 2A). Several of these males exhibited a brighter yellowish-brown dorsum than the dark brown dorsum of females. Three amplexant pairs were observed; amplexus was axillary according to the classification of Carvajal-Castro (2020) as well as for most hylids (Fig. 2B). Although Motta et al. (2012), based on an observation in an artificial pond, suggested that the species most likely lays its eggs on rigid surfaces, such as tree trunks, we recorded six egg clutches laid on the adaxial surface of herbaceous leaves from 0.5 to 2 m above the water surface in the natural habitat of the species (Fig. 2C). After hatching, the larvae probably fall into the pond, and finish development in this lentic environment, so that the species most likely presents the reproductive mode 23A of Nunes-de-Almeida et al. (2021). The record of *D. frosti* in Japurá municipality extends its geographic distribution approximately 270 km northeast from its previous nearest known distribution and its type locality (Leticia, Colombia) (Fig. 1). This is the

first record of *D. frosti* in Brazil, and the species has not yet been included in the List of Brazilian Amphibians (Segalla et al., 2021).

The reports of the occurrence of a species previously unknown to Brazil shows that vast regions of the country still have its biological richness underestimated. There is also a lack of knowledge of anuran reproductive behavior and this information would help conservation efforts and future research.

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Figure 1. Map of the known records of *Dendropsophus frosti*. The star indicates the type locality; the square indicates the locality of the paratype records. The dots indicate the two new records in the Brazilian Amazon. BR: Brazil, CO: Colombia, PE: Peru. Map was drawn using QGIS v. 3.22 (QGIS Core Team, 2022) using the limits of the South America countries provided by Tapiquén (2020).

Figure 2. Unvouchered individuals and egg clutch of *Dendropsophus frosti* observed in Tabatinga municipality during a night survey in April 2021. **A:** calling male of the species (SVL = 23.9 mm); **B:** amplexant pair with brighter male; **C:** egg clutch in a leaf above the water surface.